

Reverse Plant Breeding: A Natural Engineering for Genetic Improvement

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Manjot Kaur¹, Chaitanya Tiwari¹

¹Department of agriculture, Mata Gujri College, Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab.

Introduction

Reverse plant breeding is new and innovative plant breeding technique or meiosis engineering technique with utilization of which parental lines are produced for any kind of plant in hetero - zygos condition. Through the process of engineered meiosis parental generation in perfect homozygous condition are obtained. In this method the genetic recombination is suppressed in selected heterozygote plants by exclusion of meiotic crossing over. ²The spores i.e., male or the female obtained from such plants contain combinations of non-recombinant parental chromosomes, which can be cultured in in-vitro condition to develop homozygous doubled haploid plants.

It was proposed by Dirks *et al.* 2009 in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. The main objective of reverse breeding is to generate homozygous parental lines (complementing parents) that can be mated to recreate a desired heterozygote genotype (i.e. the initial hybrid; Wijnker *et al.* 2012). The technique of reverse breeding has not been commercialized yet and very limited work has been done.

What are Doubled Haploids?

The formation of doubled haploid is result of achiasmatic meiosis and can be developed from unfertilized ovules(gynogenesis), microspores, another culture(androgenesis), according to the well-established protocol which is applicable to both plants and crop species. The development of reverse breeding is limited upto the crops where doubled haploid is common practice. The efficiency of formation of doubled haploids differs by species to species and hence is species dependent. This breeding programme is adopted in majority of crops by different professional breeding companies in their breeding programmes. However, there are some exceptions such as soyabean, cotton, lettuce, and tomato where doubled haploid plants are rarely formed or not available at all. In modern plant breeding programmes genotyping of doubled haploids by molecular markers is routinely practiced and is also indispensable part of reverse plant breeding. In the complete absence of meiotic recombination one polymorphic molecular marker per chromosome would suffice to genotype every DH since the entire chromosome would behave as a single linkage block. In the presence of any residual crossovers, two markers (as distally located as possible) are required per chromosome.

Mechanism of Reverse Breeding

The process of reverse breeding involves essentially involves four major steps they are as follows:

Step 1: Suppression of the crossing over.

Step 2: Production of doubled haploids.

Step 3: Selection of complementary lines (parents) through marker assisted selection.

Step 4: Crossing appropriate DH lines on the basis of matching molecular markers to develop superior hybrids.

Step 1: The First Step i.e., Suppression of the Crossing Over Involves Majorly Two Stages

They are:

1. Production of gamete from heterozygote

2. Suppression of the recombination during formation of spores.

Suppression of recombination during the formation of spore, involves the suppression of gene required for the meiotic recombination. After the suppression the gene is completely knocked out by RNAi to suppress the function of DMC1 which is homologous RecA, a meiosis specific recombinase essential for the formation of crossover.

- a. The genes responsible for the meiotic recombination are:
 - i. DMC1 gene.
 - ii. RecA gene.
 - iii. SPO11 gene.

During the formation of the spores RNAi suppress down the function of these genes.

- b. Application of the exogenous chemical compound which causes the inhibition of the recombination. For example, MIRIN.

Mirin causes G2 arrest and inhibits the phosphorylation of ATM i.e., Ataxia Telangiectasia Mutated (ATM) = serine /threonine protein kinase.

What is RNAi?

RNA interference (RNAi) is an evolutionally highly conserved process of post-transcriptional gene silencing (PTGS) by which double stranded RNA (dsRNA) causes sequence specific degradation of mRNA sequences. Andrew fire and Craig Mello in the nematode worm *Caenorhabditis elegans* and later found in a wide variety of organisms including mammals.

Step 2: Production of Doubled Haploids

For the production of doubled haploids, Tissue culture of immature pollen is done. Using the technique of tissue culture which is also referred to as another culture and isolated microspore culture, immature pollen grains grow to produce colonies of mass of cells. The colonies are transferred to media with different plant growth regulators and sugars to induce growth of shoots and then roots.

Step 3: Selection of Complementary Lines i.e., Parents through the Marker Assisted Selection

During this step the complementary lines i.e. parents are selected after the production of the doubled haploids from the tissue culture which is another culture or isolated microspore culture.

Step 4: Crossing Appropriate DH Lines on the Basis of Matching Molecular Markers to Develop Superior Hybrids

At the final stage the doubled hybrid lines are selected appropriately and are crossed with each other based on the molecular markers which finally results in the formation of the superior hybrids.

Fig. The Diagram showing difference between reverse breeding and conventional breeding

Application of Reverse Breeding

1. Application in ongoing breeding programmes: Reverse breeding is still in research phase, but is clearly a technique with high potential. The main advantage of reverse breeding is that using reverse breeding, superior heterozygous plants can be produced in the F1 hybrids because of re-synthesis of parental lines.

2. Breeding on the single chromosome level: Reverse breeding, explains how chromosomes substitution lines can be obtained when reverse breeding is applied to an F1 hybrid of known parents. These homozygous chromosome substitution lines provide novel for the study of gene interactions.

3. Reverse breeding and marker assisted breeding: High throughput genotyping speeds up the process of identification of complementing parents in populations of doubled haploids. It helps in the study of gene interaction in the heterozygous inbred families.

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